

INTERLAMINAR PROPERTIES OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES WITH DIFFERENT RESIN FRACTION

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Introduction

Continuous glass fiber reinforced poly(phenylene sulfide) (PPS) composites get a lot of attention in structure engineering field due to their brilliant mechanical properties, chemical resistance, recycling and welding properties. In this work, the influence of resin fraction on the interlaminar properties of continuous glass fiber reinforced PPS (GF/PPS) composites were investigated. The GF/PPS composites were prepared by aqueous suspension prepregging and molding process. The composites were also modified with multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) and silicon carbide (SiC) whiskers in order to enhance the interlaminar properties. Short beam strength (SBS) test and double cantilever beam (DCB) test were adopted to evaluate the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness respectively. The ILSS got the maximum value at 56% fiber volume fraction. But the Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness got the maximum in high fiber volume fraction. The interlaminar properties were significantly improved with addition of MWNTs and SiC whiskers.

Influences of fiber volume fraction

The ILSS and G I C values were showed in Fig. 1. The ILSS got the maximum value at 56% fiber volume fraction and the G I C increased with the fiber volume in the range of 50%~60%. The SEM images showed that the DCB specimens with different fiber volume fraction showed similar fracture morphologies, indicating the fiber contents cannot influence the interface bonding properties. The change of interlaminar fracture toughness was attributed to the fiber bridge mechanism. High fiber volume fraction benefit to the formation of fiber bridge and improve the load absorption in crack tip, leading to high fracture toughness.

Fig 1 ILSS and G I C of GF/PPS composites with different fiber volume fraction

Fig 2 SEM images of DCB test fracture surfaces of GF/PPS composites (a) with 61% fiber volume fraction; (b) with 56% fiber volume fraction; (c) with 49% fiber volume fraction

Modified GF/PPS composites

The ILSS and G I C of GF/PPS composites were showed as follow. For ILSS, the addition of SiC whiskers got 9.4% improvement compared to unmodified composites. For G I C, the addition of 1wt% MWNTs got 20% improvement in comparison with the pristine composites. The fracture morphologies of modified composites all showed rougher fiber topographies compared with unmodified composites, indicating the increased interface properties.

Fig 3 ILSS and G I C of GF/PPS composites modified with (a) no modifier; (b) 1wt% MWNTs; (c) 1wt% SiC whiskers; (d) 0.5wt% MWNTs and 0.5wt% SiC whiskers

Fig 4 SEM images of DCB test fracture surfaces of GF /PPS composites (a) without modifier; (b) 1wt% MWNTs; (c) 1wt% SiC whiskers; (d) 0.5wt% MWNTs and 0.5wt% SiC whiskers

The toughening mechanism of MWNTs was illustrated in Fig 5. First, sub-micron sized MWNTs fillers can significantly reduce the large stress concentration on interphase by relieving the mismatch of PPS matrix and fibers. Second, MWNTs bundles were considered as rigid fillers and can serve as retardation to the growth of microcracks. And energies were consumed to pull the MWNTs out from the resin when crack propagated.

Fig 5 Illustration of crack propagation in GF /PPS composite modified with MWNTs

Interface bonding properties

The interface shear strength (IFSS) was evaluated by micro-debonding test. And the pull-out morphologies were observed by SEM. It can be found that the IFSS of PPS and glass fiber was apparently improved by the addition of MWNTs and SiC whiskers. Compared with that of pristine composites, the IFSS got 43% improvement and 50% improvement at 0.5wt% MWNTs load and 0.5wt% SiC whiskers respectively. However, excessive addition of MWNTs and SiC whiskers caused the decrease of IFSS, which was attributed to the aggregation of particles.

Fig 6 IFSS of GF and PPS modified with MWNTs and SiC whiskers

Fig 7 The pull-out morphologies of micro-debonding samples: (a) PPS; (b) with 0.5wt% MWNTs; (c) with 1.0wt% MWNTs; (d) with 1.5wt% MWNTs; (e) with 2.0wt% MWNTs; (f) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers; (g) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers; (h) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers; (i) with 0.5wt% SiC whiskers

Team Work

Fig 8 Wet powder prepregging line

Fig 9 DCB test samples